

Exploring the Evolution of Web-Based Generators and Their Impact on Language Education: A Comprehensive Analysis of Grandomastery as a Pedagogical Intervention

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The article examines the evolution of web-based generators from Web 1.0 to the present, highlighting their contemporary state with a focus on advanced technologies like quantum random number generators. The exploration spans applications in postcard exchanges, dating apps, and language teaching projects using stochastic elements. Critiquing the limitations of modern textbooks, it introduces Grandomastery as a pedagogical intervention for language teaching, tracing its development and emphasizing its unique features. The article positions Grandomastery as a supplementary tool for language learners and educators, advocating for its role in fostering creativity and enhancing language skills through a nuanced understanding.

Since the advent of Web 1.0, web-based generators have been prevalent. Brian Eno introduced generative music [1] in 1997, and the deep dream generator [2] emerged subsequently. Currently, the capacity for arbitrary randomization, encompassing self-randomization, has been facilitated by a plethora of resources. Noteworthy is the proliferation of diverse projects, beyond rudimentary functions, employing quantum random number generators [3] to achieve their objectives.

Anu.edu.au. (2011). ANU QRNG — Quantum random numbers. [online] Available at: <https://qrng.anu.edu.au/> [Accessed 23 Nov. 2021].

For aficionados of stochastic processes, programs grounded in entropy sources, such as thermal noise, hold considerable allure. The ubiquity of random functionality extends across diverse domains. In the realm of paper postcard exchange, Postcrossing [4] facilitates matches among senders by employing random addresses. Analogously, numerous dating

apps employ arbitrary matching algorithms, while platforms like Chatroulette [5] and Omegle [6] are renowned for their capacity to pair users randomly based on specified search criteria.

The domain of foreign language instruction features various initiatives dedicated to the generation of lexical units or sentences, intended for deployment in both group discussions and individual study contexts. The strategic assignment of randomized tasks emerges as a pedagogical approach conducive to proficiently addressing international examination requirements and mitigating the pervasive weariness associated with conventional textbooks characterized by a rigidly structured format. This weariness is notably conspicuous among educators who contend with recurrent utilization of identical courseware content on an annual basis.

In instances where a textbook series undergoes a revision to produce a new edition, primary modifications predominantly pertain to the incorporation of stock photographs. These visual elements, as discerned by numerous students, are perceived as serving a predominantly aesthetic purpose, ostensibly inserted to enhance the visual appeal and contemporaneity of the publication. In contrast, antiquated textbooks frequently featured cleverly crafted illustrations, meticulously hand-drawn to align with the subject matter, capturing phenomena and themes that contemporary editors might refrain from endorsing due to their adherence to principles of equality, diversity, inclusion, and tolerance.

A firm handshake is considered a sign of good character and self-confidence. A weak handshake is considered a sign of a weak, ineffective, or very gentle person. "That person shakes hands like a dead fish," someone might say of a person whose hand is limp. Ask Americans to show you the proper handshake grip if you are in doubt.

An Indispensable Guide to Dangerous English 2000

Amazon.com. (2021). *Dangerous English 2000: An Indispensable Guide for Language Learners and Others*: Claire, Elizabeth: 9781887744089: Amazon.com: Books. [online] Available at: <https://www.amazon.com/Dangerous-English-2000-Indispensable-Language/dp/1887744088> [Accessed 22 Nov. 2021].

The prevalence of depersonalized stock imagery in present-day printed educational materials theoretically should have undergone obsolescence. In the 21st century, the efficacy of captivating or motivating individuals through comprehensive, full-color publications predominantly populated by unremarkable stock photographs, coupled with a limited array of activities centered around discussion topics or speaking exercises, is notably diminished.

Furthermore, a considerable cohort of language learners, even among the younger demographic, concedes to perusing the contents of textbooks preemptively, often immediately post-acquisition. This pre-exposure results in a lack of anticipation or enthusiasm for exploring novel topics or engaging with new modules. This phenomenon can be attributed to students' innate curiosity or, alternatively, their proclivity for novel stimuli. Upon a cursory review of textbook pages, students frequently find the presented subjects and visual materials overly familiar and seemingly trivial, given their pervasive presence across contemporary educational literature.

Modern instructional materials manifest an additional limitation wherein authors tend to concentrate on a select few central themes, frequently reiterated across different proficiency levels. Common thematic focal points in general English classes encompass interpersonal relationships, contemporary communication modalities, employment, entertainment, travel, and housing. Superficially, these thematic elements, coupled with their

corresponding vocabulary and grammar constructs, ostensibly address a broad spectrum of expressive and perceptual language skills. However, it is evident that a singular textbook cannot comprehensively encompass the array of topics that have emerged in recent years, postdating the entire trajectory of textbook creation, publication, and distribution.

Notably, foreign language educators express a degree of discomfort when encountering outdated technological representations, antiquated browser window designs reminiscent of the Internet 1.0 era, and obsolete applications, programs, and websites within instructional materials. Such antiquated elements are often strategically incorporated to circumvent copyright concerns and reduce licensing expenditures, a practice observed even among publishing behemoths such as Longman, Oxford, and Cambridge, despite their substantial financial turnovers.

Fundamentally, the oversights of textbook developers elude comprehensive consideration by both students and educators. The conspicuous nature of such obsolescence would be mitigated through regular updates to instructional materials. Regrettably, this practice is not consistently implemented, leading to a discernible decline in the enthusiasm and motivation of language learners. Students exhibit limited tolerance for academic textbooks characterized by the predominance of unstimulating, conventional subjects, typically accompanied by mundane photographic content from standard libraries. The dispensation of such textbooks by educators instigates an anticipation of a monotonous progression in their language acquisition journey among learners.

Nevertheless, a heightened level of concern arises when considering the prospect of the textbook assuming a solitary role in the pedagogical arsenal of educators, unless it is supplemented with mundane PowerPoint presentations featuring visually cluttered materials, thereby inducing a diminution in student interest and potential annoyance. Moreover, the prevalence of self-generated resources is characterized by frequent infringements on copyright, the absence of source attribution, and a display of suboptimal design aesthetics.

The Origins of Grandomastery

In its nascent stage, Grandomastery [7] emerged as a rudimentary application tailored for Android 1.3 devices, denominated as Random ESL Questions. Notably, accredited IELTS experts availed themselves of this application for the purpose of task generation specifically designed for the Speaking component of the test.

The description of ESL Random Questions App

For several years I have been collecting more than 1000 conversation questions for the learners of English from a wide variety of books and websites and now they are neatly accumulated in this add-free app. It works offline, but if you want to share discussion questions with your students, colleagues and friends, you can use social buttons to share the question in social networks. The questions are most suitable for students of Intermediate, Upper-Intermediate or Advanced levels for discussion or as essay topics. With this app you can always have exciting ready-made lessons in your pocket! If you have any interesting questions you'd like to add or you want some of the questions removed from the app, please, let me know!

Some sources that have been used apart from my personal collection:
 The Complete Book of Questions: 1001 Conversation Starters for Any Occasion (Garry D. Poole)
 The Book of Questions: Revised and Updated (Gregory Stock Ph.D.)
 The Great Book of Questions and Answers: Over 1000 Questions and Answers (Arcturus Editorial Board)
 Let's Talk About It: 1000 Questions for Conversation (Craig Drayton, Mark Gibbon)

APKPure.com. (2015). APKPure. [online] Available at: <https://apkpure.com/id/esl-random-questions/com.eslquestions> [Accessed 22 Nov. 2021].

Chronologically, Random ESL Questions underwent a transformative evolution, metamorphosing into the Grandmastery website. In its initial iteration, the website encompassed analogous activities, featuring randomized questions [8] spanning a diverse array of topics. Subsequently, the platform exhibited progressive expansion, culminating in the incorporation of 45 distinct activities [9]. Noteworthy is the migration of certain activities, previously confined to paper-based formats, onto the digital platform.

Grandmastery. (2015). Question | Grandmastery. [online] Available at: <https://www.grandmastery.com/question> [Accessed 22 Nov. 2021].

One cognitive engagement, referred to as "Random Proverbs," involves affixing antecedent lexical units to magnetized cards within a classroom milieu. The originator of this activity intricately fashioned a comprehensive array of magnets, each featuring widely recognized English proverbs. Students were explicitly instructed to reproduce these proverbs on marker boards, with a focus on cultivating absurdity and humor. It is noteworthy that the attention garnered by these endeavors increased proportionally to the extent of their grammatical and lexical accuracy, underscoring the imperative for novelty within the parameters of linguistic correctness.

Imgur (2021). Random Magnets Activity in real ESL classroom environment — Album on Imgur. [online] Imgur. Available at: <https://imgur.com/gallery/Ogy0CJY> [Accessed 22 Nov. 2021].

Adolescents inherently exhibit a proclivity for the generation of idiosyncratic verbal compositions rather than mere replication of existing content. Even when confronted with Palmer's lookup tables, teenagers tend to approach these tasks with a penchant for humor, absurdity, and eccentricity, thereby transforming the activity into an instructive learning experience. An observed phenomenon among educators is the challenge students encounter in eliminating unconventional variants during tasks. Paradoxically, on an emotional level, students demonstrate reluctance to discard answers, albeit erroneous, if they possess a humorous or original quality. This reluctance appears to be a confluence of age-related factors and a inclination to eschew conventional correctness in favor of maintaining an amusing and unique perspective. Conventional correct responses are perceived as lacking in inspirational and creative elements, devoid of a punchline or absurdist quality, rendering them unsuitable for dissemination on platforms such as Twitter. In stark contrast, the utilization of Random Proverbs [10] empowers learners to formulate novel statements within the confines of grammatical norms, fostering an environment conducive to self-expression.

Grandmastery. (2015). Magnets | Grandmastery. [online] Available at: <https://www.grandmastery.com/magnets> [Accessed 22 Nov. 2021].

These expressions may encompass components originating from widely recognized proverbs; however, the primary appeal for Grandmastery users

lies in the satirical deconstruction of conventional phrases and the exploration of novel semantic interpretations.

Furthermore, another Grandomastery activity entails composing a narrative that integrates a closed sequence of lexical units. The intention is to develop diverse iterations of the Random Story [11] activity tailored to varying proficiency levels and fields of expertise among learners.

Grandomastery. (2015). Story | Grandomastery. [online] Available at: <https://www.grandomastery.com/story> [Accessed 22 Nov. 2021].

The execution of these tasks requires a significant investment of time and effort.

Grandomastery tasks, such as Random Abstractions [12], center on abstract concepts, engaging participants in the identification of parallels between ostensibly dissimilar abstract notions. A pivotal component of Grandomastery is rooted in the principle of bisociation, propounded by the eminent author and philosopher Arthur Koestler in his work "The Act of Creation." Creativity, in essence, involves the interconnection of disparate domains, such as art, science, and humor. Bisociation materializes when two ostensibly incongruous planes intersect, leading to the unexpected convergence of diverse phenomena and formations. This principle mirrors the structure observed in jokes, where the climax or punch line embodies the irony, and the greater the unpredictability of the punch line, the more captivating the joke becomes. Analogously, the Grandomastery Integrative Thinking Platform manifests a comparable principle during the execution of its exercises.

Juvenile individuals exhibit an inherent proclivity towards demiurgic tendencies, particularly evident in their aptitude for devising novel narratives, expressions, and lexicon. Conversely, mature individuals, even at advanced proficiency levels, experience heightened constraints governed by established linguistic norms. Conventional and conservative educational establishments tend to

instill apprehension in all students regarding the precision of their task fulfillment, prompting pervasive concerns such as: "How should I articulate this? Are there specific elements to include in my response? Is there a temporal constraint? Can I provide a more extensive answer? What constitutes an optimal response? Is the inclusion of an illustrative example imperative?" This phenomenon persists even in tasks devoid of explicit limitations, presupposing that the grammatical and semantic constituents are wholly contingent upon the volition and inclination of the students.

The prevailing excessive formalism and didacticism within contemporary textbooks and assessments contribute significantly to the establishment of a psychological framework akin to Stockholm syndrome, albeit within an educational methodology context. From the initial stages of language acquisition, students are compelled to assume roles akin to instructional designers. The meticulous reading and comprehension of task instructions are imperative, demanding a strict adherence to any provided dichotomies or modular structures. For instance, if an exercise is bifurcated into segments labeled as a) and b), learners are obligated to adhere to this categorical division. Furthermore, within modules dedicated to specific grammar constructions, learners are consistently expected to employ these constructions in diverse speaking tasks and exercises.

The communicative approach, reminiscent of a somewhat authoritarian regime, imposes constraints on both freedom of speech and action, indicating a limited temporal relevance. Many experts advocate for the prospective replacement of communicative language teaching with systematic language teaching, infused with abstract, analytical, heuristic, and conceptual thinking approaches, attributes ostensibly lacking in modern courseware and language assessments. Criticisms of the communicative method include its purported focus on an excessively narrow spectrum of topics and the perceived simplicity of the taught communication skills. In contrast, a modern textbook often fails to afford students the opportunity to scrutinize a sentence from diverse perspectives, as exemplified by the Grandomastery Random Statement Activity, which fosters a multifaceted exploration of language problems.

its challenges, particularly concerning the reinforcement of grammatical or lexical skills within individual units or modules. Complete activation of a skill necessitates the incorporation of supplementary resources. It is noteworthy that a majority of online resources do not adhere to even the most basic design standards, often resembling Word Art from Word 97. Notably, materials sourced from popular online platforms like busyteacher [13], iSLCollective [14], and ESLPrintables [15] frequently present issues related to both visual aesthetics and content. These concerns persist across materials targeting diverse age groups, as even resources explicitly designed for adults may incorporate clipart featuring outdated frames from the previous century, superfluous, inappropriate, and disorganized decorative elements. Furthermore, the text in such materials may concurrently feature italicization, bolding, underlining, and be presented in unconventional and aesthetically displeasing color combinations.

TO BE / HAVE GOT REVIEW

1. Fill in the blanks with the present of **to be**:

- your friend at school now? Yes, he
- We (not) happy today.
- It sunny and hot in summer.
- your parents in the kitchen? No, they
- The books on the desk.
- these your pencils? Yes, they
- The new George Clooney's film really good.
- Carol and Pam (not) at school today, they ill.
- Munich in France? No, it
- Our neighbours very noisy.
- Where my keys? I can't find them!

2. Complete the sentences with **have/ has got**:

- Mary a baby brother? Yes, she
- My friends (not) a big house.
- Our school a canteen and a new lab.
- How many pens you three.
- My sister a boyfriend called Thomas.
- The Jones (not) a garden.
- The new hotel 132 rooms.
- the students a lot of homework? No, they
- Our dog some puppies.
- How much sugar this coffee? It's very sweet.
- Some of my schoolmates (not) enough money to buy the books.

3. Fill in the gaps with the correct form of **to be** or **have got**:

- Mary ten years old.
- My brother short, blond hair.
- (you) a dictionary? Yes, I
- It usually very cold in winter.
- Where the children?
- The apples on the table and we meat in the fridge.
- How much money (Mr Rockefeller), mum? He very rich, Tony!
- The school bus late this morning.
- This Mr Swan. He a son and a daughter.
- Who they? The Williams, of course.
- When Tina's birthday party? It next Saturday.
- How many brothers or sisters

4. Say if the sentences are **R** (right) or **W** (wrong). **Correct the mistakes**.

- We haven't got blue eyes.
- Is the baby got in its cradle?
- The old church has got 250 years old.
- Everybody are at the party.
- Are you English on Monday and Friday? Yes, we have.
- It has got rainy and windy today.
- Have you got cold, Peter?
- How many days is February? It's twenty-eight days.
- These boys have got identical schoolbags; they have got blue and white.
- What's the matter, Tom? Are you flu?
- Our garden is a lot of flowers. These are my favourite.
- Sally has got on holiday this week.
- There hasn't got a cinema near the park.
- Mary and Tom are lots of friends.

MAKE or DO

Fill in the blanks with the correct form of **MAKE** or **DO**

1. Mr Jones a lot of money when he sold his company.

2. My parents the gardening at weekends.

3. Sally the homework with her father.

4. The candidate lots of speeches during the campaign.

5. The company profit since they have changed their policy.

6. Tim the washing once a week.

7. Clowns try to people laugh, but they don't always succeed.

8. Mum the shopping every Friday after work.

9. They business with a British company.

10. I always the washing up after lunch.

11. Dad likes the ironing. He it every Saturday.

12. The maid the beds after the guests have left the room.

13. My sister yoga on Mondays and Wednesdays.

14. Mr Black a mistake with his password, so he couldn't log in.

15. I'm sorry, but John an important phone call now.

16. We a wonderful journey to Italy last summer. We went to Pisa and Rome.

17. Mr Baker delicious

18. Pam the

19. Dad the

20. My mother and her friends

Google.com. (2012). esl printables — Google Search. [online] Available at: https://www.google.com/search?q=esl+printables&newwindow=1&sxsrf=AOaemvIBEJpncRAnhf2PRy6MQsgZvTOHWw:1637008746882&source=Inms&tbm=isch&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwjA7efmJv0AhU4RzABhdHFAp4Q_AUoAXoECAEQAw&biw=1280&bih=689&dp=2#imgrc=nmMTHi00K_GKuM [Accessed 23 Nov. 2021].

It is remarkable that despite the advent of Web 4.0, there persists a demand for aesthetically displeasing handouts. Notably, these suboptimal resources continue to be maintained by their creators, with a significant portion being commercially available and evidently well-received. This phenomenon suggests a deficiency in both the creators' and users' foundational aesthetic and technical competencies. Furthermore, the prevalence of Comic Sans worksheets featuring distorted, low-resolution graphics without discernible color schemes or coherent design principles is noteworthy. Similar challenges manifest on social media platforms such as Instagram and Facebook, where visual clutter, often animated, prevails. Distinctions between these resources lie in the use of stock images instead of clipart and the employment of the Lobster typeface as opposed to Comic Sans. Seth Godin, a renowned marketing guru and author of a highly regarded book on marketing, strongly advocates for chief executives of major corporations to undergo in-person design courses. Such courses would enable them to firsthand comprehend the principles underpinning modern, comprehensible, and functionally effective high-quality design.

A preliminary examination of materials commonly employed by educators of foreign languages prompts a parallel suggestion to our counterparts. This is especially pertinent considering that corporate executives typically have dedicated design teams at their disposal, in contrast to educators and trainers who often resort to crafting their instructional materials, referred to as "worksheets" or "printables," utilizing rudimentary tools such as a basic text editor or MS Paint.

Undoubtedly, there exist projects of commendable quality that manifest exceptional visual design; nevertheless, the predominant portion of these resources adheres to a pay-per-use model, caters to individual usage, or is exclusively accessible through paid applications.

In the context of Grandomastery, the creator openly acknowledges that the project falls short of achieving design excellence. Despite undergoing multiple revisions and simplifications, there remains ample room for improvement, albeit with positive dynamics stemming from these alterations. Notably, in 2021, both the Amazon Associates and Abebooks affiliate programs were discontinued, thereby eliminating the potential for revenue generation even through banner ads. Grandomastery's activities are deliberately presented with minimal visual clutter, incorporating relevant images only when deemed absolutely necessary. For instance, the Random Image Activity [16] introduces students to image-description practice based on a randomly selected image, accompanied by nontrivial questions about the

artwork, thereby facilitating the development of a monologue speech of a distinctly creative nature.

Grandomastery. (2015). Image | Grandomastery. [online] Available at: <https://www.grandomastery.com/image> [Accessed 22 Nov. 2021].

In an ancillary observation, Random Images stands as one facet of Grandomastery activities, encompassing not only the generation of objects but also incorporating supporting structures to facilitate students' acquisition of speech functions without succumbing to repetitiveness. This unique feature extends to tasks being generated for both teachers and students, rendering each task an unpredictable experience for individual participants. It is paramount to cultivate an environment of unpredictability, particularly because the exhaustive evaluation of continuously updated resources with dynamically generated activities can lead to participant burnout. Despite the evident advantages of stochastic task generation for speaking practice, numerous teachers, including native speakers, voice concerns that real-time task generation impedes their ability to prepare for a lesson or training in advance. It is acknowledged that a trainer's comprehensive familiarity with content prior to its "presentation" to students may result in diminished interest in the teaching process and an escalation of educators' concealed irritation to varying degrees of success. Long-term adherence to a specific course framework exacerbates the challenge of concealing annoyance, particularly when students encounter difficulties with textbook exercises that the teacher has virtually memorized. In contrast, simultaneous exposure of the teacher and student to a novel exercise mitigates the disparity in their perceptions of the displayed information, thereby facilitating the teacher's understanding of the student's perspective.

Remarkably, Grandomastery affords the user the capability to generate individual tasks by activating the corresponding task-specific button. Additionally, users can select the type of activity by engaging the "Random" button situated in the upper left corner. The Random script is underpinned by what are referred to as "weights," denoting the frequency with which a particular activity type is generated. Notably, activities such as Random Question enjoy a higher

frequency of display owing to their inherent versatility, boasting an extensive pool of over 3000 questions. In contrast, activities tailored for specific purposes, such as Random Job Interview Activity [17], are less frequently generated and cater to individuals seeking to hone spontaneous speech skills.

Certainly, the Grandomastery platform would be suboptimal for conversation clubs or creative games were it not for the capacity to systematically execute the entire cycle of 45 tasks in a randomized sequence. This functionality is facilitated through the utilization of the CYCLE button, conveniently located in the upper right corner.

In augmentation of our conventional platform designed for the generation of diverse tasks catering to ESL learners, Grandomastery presents an exclusive segment dedicated to integrative thinking exercises. These exercises prove beneficial not only for individuals learning English as a foreign language but also for native English speakers seeking to enhance their improvisational and spontaneous speech skills. Moreover, these exercises serve as a valuable tool for employers assessing the creative acumen of candidates during interviews. According to insights from our human resources counterparts, such exercises not only alleviate stress but also provide candidates with a platform to showcase their proficiency in integrative thinking.

The quality and diversity of content on Grandomastery undergo continuous refinement. The platform is dedicated to alleviating constraints and encouraging participants to scrutinize various phenomena, often of a negative nature, along with overlooked and sidestepped social constructs, from an entirely novel perspective, yielding distinctive and unconventional interpretations.

In this article, we have addressed the challenges confronting the English language teaching sector, particularly the discernible deficiencies in contemporary educational courseware. It is imperative to clarify that Grandomastery does not present itself as a substitute for well-structured teaching materials, nor does it advocate against the use of language textbooks. However, in response to the dearth of exercises fostering the enhancement and application of speaking skills, Grandomastery assumes a role as a supplementary educational and engaging instrument. While edutainment is commonly associated with gamification, the term does not uniformly denote online accolades, animated effects, and augmented reality. Grandomastery embodies a cyber-vintage concept—an amalgamation of authentic vintage materials and contemporary virtual elements such as a spectrogram for assessing speech fluency. This amalgamation has the potential to yield unforeseeable and fortuitous

outcomes, conducive to spontaneous discoveries. Serving as a compendium, Grandomastery endeavors to furnish a resource for individuals keen on practicing and instructing integrative, productive, and higher-order thinking.

Alexander Popov, a certified TESOL English educator and resource specialist, has garnered recognition, including accolades such as the HundrED Showcase Award, Educational Influencer Award, Microsoft Innovative Educator Expert Award, and ESL Treasures Award, showcasing his accomplishments in the field.

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